

MEDIA DISCOURSE AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article studies features of media discourse in Uzbek and English languages; The main research focus is made on theoretical and practical basis of media discourse. Author of this article made a conclusion about measures effectiveness that are used by linguists.

Key words: discourse, media discourse, linguistics, critical discourse analysis, lexicon, speech. The foundation of the linguistic theory of text and discourse in the middle of the 20th century was in line with broader studies on the communicative nature of language. Recent studies have considered discourse on the level of social and mental processes explained both by linguistic and extralinguistic factors. The extra-linguistic factors cover the specifics of discourse types, genres, sub-genres and the relevant requirements imposed on them. Therefore, discourse can be defined as a very complex phenomenon with linguistic, psychological, social and cultural dimensions. Traditionally discourses are divided into three broad types: 1) literary; 2) institutional (media, political, etc.); and 3) academic or scientific. According to Fairclough, genre or type may be characterized as a “socially ratified way of using language in connection with a particular type of social activity”. For example, the core of the informative function of language exists in media texts, i.e., topic and extra-linguistic reality, including reported real-life events and stories. Media texts and media discourses are produced, first of all, to inform people by delivering various types of messages. According to Pearce, “Mass communication, however, is the process by which a person, group of people, or large organization creates a message and transmits it through some type of medium to a large, anonymous, heterogeneous audience”. The crucial factor here is a medium/media (serving as a bridge between the senders of a message and the audience) and its/their type. Furthermore, Pearce writes: “Until recently, defining mass media was easy. Mass media were comprised of eight traditional industries: books, newspapers, magazines, radio, movies, television and the Internet.

New technologies have made serious changes in this traditional classification of media industries, adding also social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and Viber, as well as blogs, amongst other media. There are numerous monographs, textbooks, edited volumes and scholarly papers concerning media discourse from interdisciplinary perspectives including media studies, systemic-functional linguistics, semiotics, discourse analysis, critical discourse analysis and cognitive linguistics. In these and many other studies, media discourse and its numerous genres and sub-genres have been analyzed with the application of various methods and theoretical approaches. Making reference to this solid background, the present volume has a broader aim with an equal focus on a combination of these issues, and especially on a correlation between the traditional and the novel in the media, both in contemporary as well as in historical times. New insights into this area can reshape our understanding of the media, which in turn reflects both life and society and thus can shape distinct or new visions. There are three main overarching themes pursued in the volume: 1) media discourse and language (literal and figurative); 2) media discourse and genre analysis; and 3) the main trends in new media discourse. Due to the Internet and globalization, as well as to the

development and worldwide distribution of satellite channels, students taking a course in foreign journalism can easily watch programs on BBC News, Euronews and Bloomberg TV Europe. Work realities for journalists have also changed: having demolished the once strong Iron Curtain, online media have turned into truly transboundary media. Contemporary students know English which now performs as a New Latin of global media. At their disposal they have both on-line web-based multimedia and traditional news media posted on the Internet. The new generic features of mass media include hypertext links, multimedia, interactive techniques and transgenic characteristics. New consumers have no difficulty orientating in multimedia content. Blogs on the web-sites of traditional media, once printed, introduce a new personage of a prosumer. The User Generated Content (UGC) is constantly moderated on media web-sites. Principles that a convergent editorial board adheres to in performing their work are continuous 24 / 7 monitoring of news lines. Students don't find it hard to understand media metrics and online media sociology.

The term "discourse" is a complex and mammoth-like interpretation. Many previous studies mention the term discourse as very ambiguous since its introduction to modern science and the various broad interpretations of discourse. Therefore, the definition of discourse reflected here will focus on the linguistics point of view, especially that of applied linguistics. Here, it refers to the speech patterns and how language, dialects, and acceptable statements are used in a particular community. Discourse as a subject of study looks at discourse among people who share the same speech conventions.

To analyze the "discourse" especially written discourse such as articles of journal, Linguistic study provides a scientific studies named discourse analysis (henceforth DA) as a methodology to understand the linguistic phenomenology of a discourse in particular situation like economic journal as what Carter (1993), defines discourse analysis as a way of examining the use of language in different speech communities and to discover patterns either in spoken or written forms as well as their correlation with the societies. Written discourse can be viewed from various angles in accordance to what the readers focus on and can be approached from a variety of disciplinary perspectives and purposes. Therefore, this present study seen the written discourse analysis of journal articles can systematically describing the ideas and the relations among the ideas that readers read as well as what writers write. The method draws on work in a number of disciplines, such as rhetoric, text linguist and psychology. These disciplines provide ways to describe and analyze how the structure and content of the texts encode ideas and the relations among ideas.

The media discourse in the information space of the university implements informative and representative functions and has a significant impact on the image of the university both in the academic and scientific environment, and in society as a whole. The purpose of the media discourse analysis is to describe them image of an educational institution, which is attractive to students, scientists, the business environment, and the dissemination of innovations in education and science. The authors of the article provide an overview of theories of media discourse, characterized various approaches to determining the information space of a university. While studying the media discourse represented on the websites of the universities in English and Russian languages, the main attention was given to the analysis of the news texts, comparison of methods of transmitting information in different languages. Concurrently, the genre diversity of texts and the specifics of the presenting information using

infographics, hyperlinks, photographs, sound, and interactivity are taken into account. The study focuses on the information space of the university, which combines information and telecommunication systems and networks, information technologies for their maintenance and use. The website is considered as the main tool for the interaction of the university internal and external environment. The use of several languages in a media discourse emphasizes its functional focus on intercultural interaction with a diverse audience.

At present, there is a tendency to shift the center of research interests to the problems of mass media and mass speech influence. The mechanisms of influence on the audience are studied, linguistic means of influence are identified and analyzed using examples of certain types of discourse: political, religious, advertising, including mass media discourse. In linguistics, arguments about the concept of discourse give rise to many theories. Discourse is represented as a set of statements, a speech stream, a way of speaking, a text in a situation, a reflection of mentality and ideology in the text. The media discourse as a component of the university's information space attracts research interest due to the media discourse capacity to connect the university with the society and contribute to the third university mission – connection of its activities with socio-economic context. For the linguist this discourse may become the source of the new discursive and linguistic features of a text published within information space of the university. When determining the media discourse, there are two approaches. According to the first, media discourse is a specific type of speech-making activity, which is unique to the information field of mass media. In this sense, it is necessary to distinguish between media discourse and other independent types of discourse, such as political, religious, scientific, etc. According to the second approach, media discourse is thought of as any kind of discourse implemented in the field of mass communication, produced by the media. Thus, we can talk about political, religious, pedagogical, and other types of media discourse, implying that for their implementation, these types of institutional discourse presuppose a relatively stable set of practices for the production, broadcast, and interpretation of mass media.

From the stated above we may come to the conclusion that media discourse is integrated into social, personal and professional relationships and can be used to achieve appropriate illocutionary effect. Media discourse is a leading type of discourse that penetrates into all types of institutional and everyday communication. Media texts become significant means of forming society outlook and world perception of individuals. Our analysis shows that due to the competent content of news texts and correctly constructed visual communications, the site plays a great role in promoting the university image. Though it is impossible to count the number of the website visitors to correlate it with the particular discourse, the certain analytical data obtained as a result of the media discourse analysis can be used to correct the University's communication policy. The news block is located in the center of the page of the official site and is an internal site represented by announcements and current events. Analysis of news reports revealed a positive emotional color of texts, which positively affects the recipient's perception of the university's activities.

References:

1. www.ziyonet.com